

Knowledge Management System: A Tool for Disaster Risk Reduction Management of Local Municipalities

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Abstract:- A disaster risk mitigation plan is important, and it necessitates expertise in order to make informed decisions and organize action during disasters. In response to disaster risk reduction, the municipal government introduces initiatives such as health care, business facilities, sanitation, and livelihood. These systems, on the other hand, lack inventory and control. The knowledge management framework was created in response to this issue. It aimed to develop barangay surveillance systems and a database that would be useful in the event of a disaster. The information management framework used application software and programming languages, which were driven by the system creation life cycle. With graphical images and charts, it can identify evacuation areas closest to the barangay. The system also included an inventory of available facilities and actual disaster equipment, as well as the approximate travel time and mode of transportation from each barangay and evacuation area. The evaluation result received a high score, indicating that the established system was operationally sound. The developed system aided in the provision of critical information during disasters and calamities, especially in the development of disaster risk mitigation plans for the four municipal offices and 38 barangays of Occidental Mindoro, Philippines.

Keywords:- information technology, knowledge management system, KMS, MDRRMO, system development, Philippines.

I. INTRODUCTION

Collecting, saving, filing, retrieving, and tracking data has never been easier thanks to technological advancements. Information is captured, stored, and exchanged as a result of this process. It is a device capable of storing and exchanging organizational expertise of information technology.

A knowledge management system is an IT system that stores and retrieves information in order to enhance comprehension, coordination, and process alignment. The knowledge management system [1], is a solution for documenting, recording, and managing information provided by organizations in their day-to-day operations. It offers tools for organizing, consolidating, and making indexing and retrieval of a company's institutional knowledge and information easier for customer service and internal support, resulting in increased employee performance and productivity.

The Republic Act 10121, otherwise known as the Philippine Disaster Reduction and Management Act section 12 article 12, mandating that each MDRRMO should “maintain a database of human resource, equipment, directories, and location of critical infrastructures and their capacities such as hospitals and evacuation centers”, a knowledge management system will be developed. So, to comply with this mandate, a knowledge management system was proposed. By removing the need for manual inventory logging and sorting, this device assisted the MDRRMO in gathering and tracking thousands of data points. It also ensures that residents receive prompt and efficient service, as well as that the agency's records are reliable and safe. The municipalities of San Jose, Magsaysay, Rizal, and Calintaan (SAMARICA), Municipal Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office (MDRRMO), were the study's target region.

A. Conceptual Framework

Fig. 1: Research Paradigm

The study followed the IPO framework in carrying out the objectives of the study. As shown in figure 1, there are three categories considered for the inputs: (1) knowledge requirement, (2) software requirements, and (3) hardware requirements. While in the process, the SDLC model for software development was used. Lastly, the output expected is the Knowledge Management System for MDRRMO of SAMARICA municipalities.

B. Objectives of the Study

The study aimed to develop a knowledge management system for the Municipal Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office (MDRRMO) of SAMARICA municipalities.

Specifically, the study aims to develop a knowledge management system with the following features:

- monitoring control for Social Services, Planning, Disaster, Materials, Equipment, and Evacuation Areas;
- data population of the municipality;
- information list of every barangay needed by the agency; and
- a user-friendly system.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Knowledge is often called the intellectual capital of an organization that is gained through years of experiences [2]. In the strategic management literature, a knowledge-based perspective of the organization has emerged. Furthermore, according to Dorasamy, Raman, and Kaliannan (2012), effective emergency management requires careful preparation, guided response, and well-coordinated efforts during the emergency management life cycle.

Knowledge Management (KM) is commonly used in forming strategic alliances in an organization [3]. An efficient use of resources and facilities so that the company can get more value out of its human and technological investments. At the same time, this contributes to the organization's overall efficiency.

The type of information related to the disaster situation, as well as the appropriate technologies to handle the knowledge, are extremely important in speeding up the search, rescue, relief, and overall Disaster Management process [4]. Local people's knowledge, gained through several years of experience, is invaluable in assisting in the prevention of disasters. However, since they include perspectives, values, observations, and conventional effective approaches, they may not be available or understood by officers in charge appointed by disaster management organizations. Tacit knowledge (local knowledge) can be identified, implicit knowledge can be transformed to explicit, and computerization of explicit knowledge using relevant information technology applications such as networking and DBMS can help incorporate science and local knowledge in disaster management organizations.

Similarly, Knowledge Management Systems (KMS) enable disaster management collaboration, exchanging information on risk mitigation activities, alert systems, and emergency response, all of which reduce disaster impact [5].

To effectively improve the city's emergency decision-making capabilities and reduce the risk of unforeseen accidents. By introducing knowledge management theory and systematically analyzing the classification and function of knowledge in the intercity emergency decision-making management system [6], it would be possible to achieve the obtaining, transferring, applying, and sharing of city emergency decision-making knowledge, as well as improve

the knowledge utilization rate. Scientific and efficient knowledge management can provide reliable information for emergency decision-making in a timely manner, allowing for more scientific and practical rescue decisions to be made quickly and effectively. As a result, a data management system geared toward intercity emergency decision-making was created, which has practical implications for improving the entire urban emergency management capability.

Reference [7] indicated that in order to improve KMS efficiency, the quality dimensions should be found first. As a result of advancements in information technology, knowledge management systems are becoming more complex and diverse. Users' demands for more effective and efficient KMS systems are increasing awareness and desire for KMS efficiency.

III. METHODOLOGY

The study followed the procedure of system development covering the following:

A. Project Design

The Knowledge Management System is a database system that facilitates timely recording of data in order to generate necessary records. The user can easily update the disaster equipment, evacuation center, and record of households in the system and the Administrator can automatically verify and check all the records using the system.

B. Project Development

The system development life cycle consists of the following steps: Data Gathering, Designing, Coding, System Enhancements, and Evaluation and Testing of the output project, was followed.

C. Operation Procedures

- Install the program.
- Load the program. A log in form will appear for the Admin user account name and password.
- Enter the Admin user account name. The user will provide the appropriate user account name to access the system.
- View the information. In this form, the Admin can view the Map which holds the information about Record of Households, Evacuation Centers, and Disaster Equipment distributed to each barangay.
- Edit the Information. In this form, the Admin can manage the KMS.
- Reports. The user can produce processed data.

D. Testing Procedures

- Functionality and flexibility testing was done using the different 32 & 64-bit Windows Operating System such as 7 Ultimate, 8.1 Pro, and 10.
- Functionality testing of the system using dimension with screen resolution of 1366x768, 1280x768, and 800x600.
- Capability and compatibility testing using the internal video card with minimum of 1GB.
- Compatibility testing with the memory of 1GB, 2GB, and 4GB RAM.

E. Evaluation Procedures

- Preliminary Evaluation- Preliminary evaluation of the developer on the expected output was conducted.
- Project Demonstration
 - A total of 20 IT personnel, 10 officers from Municipal Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office, and 10 IT experts/programmers were requested to evaluate the system.
 - The researchers presented the system to each MDRRMO of SAMARICA municipalities.
 - The respondents were asked to operate the system and to observe its performance.
- Final Evaluation
 - Evaluation survey was distributed among respondents composed of 20 randomly selected IT personnel, 10 officers from Municipal Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office, and 10 IT experts/programmers.
 - Asked the respondents to rate the system based on the criteria of the evaluation instrument and to provide their comments and recommendations using the five-point Likert Scale.

Before the system implementation, a permit from MDRRMO was secured by the researchers, as well as the certificate of utilization from the beneficiary municipalities after the conduct of the study.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section presents the project description and structure, capabilities, limitations, and project evaluation.

A. Project Description

The Knowledge Management System enabled the personnel of the Municipal Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office to give efficient service to the barangays of SAMARICA municipalities of Occidental Mindoro by identifying and providing plans for evacuation during disaster. The system provided manageable database for the agency with the administrator’s handling all the functions such as adding, removing, manipulating, and updating of data each barangay, the evacuation areas, and disaster equipment.

B. Project Structure

The KMS for MDRRMO consists of a log-in page, homepage, and barangay page.

Fig. 2: Screenshots of the developed system.

The set of images in Fig.2, are the screenshots of the KMS. The Login Page in image 1 allowed the administrator and users of the system to retrieve access and permissions of using the system. Images 3 and 4 contains information of each municipalities where LGU offices and Hotline numbers are displayed.

The contents are different in each municipality, as well as the design. However, the functionality and outputs are the same as needed by the MDRRMO.

To test the capability of the system, it undergone testing on different computer and components. It was good that the system was developed with a user-friendly interface the

adopts with the different computers where it was installed. The system runs best at OS Windows 8, 64-bit, monitor size of 16" and a memory capacity of 4 gigabytes. All the testing procedure was successfully implemented.

C. Project Evaluation

There were a total 40 respondents who evaluated the system, 20 MDRRMO personnel, 5 in each municipality, and 20 users who are staff of the municipal hall. Using the ISO 9126-1 evaluation tool for software development, an evaluation summary result in Table 1 was gathered and tabulated showing the mean per criteria and the corresponding interpretation.

Criteria	Mean	Interpretation
Functionality	4.57	Excellent
Content	4.59	Excellent
Reliability	4.12	Very Good
Availability	4.18	Very Good
Salability	4.23	Very Good
Grand Mean	4.34	Very Good

Table 1: Summary of Evaluation

Legend: 4.51-5.50 – Excellent; 3.51-4.50 - Very Good; 2.51-3.50 – Good; 1.51-2.50 – Fair; 0.50-1.50– Poor

The criteria functionality and content got an “Excellent” rating with means 4.57 and 4.59 respectively. All of the other criteria got the “Very Good” rating which result to a grand mean of 4.34 which was also interpreted as “Very Good.” The result proved that the system is functional and recommended for use.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In consideration of the objectives of the study and the result of testing and evaluation carried out, it was concluded that the Knowledge Management System for Municipal Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office for the SAMARICA Area of Occidental Mindoro was successfully developed with the following features:

- Has monitoring control for Social Services, Planning, Disaster, Materials, Equipment, and Evacuation Areas;
- Consisted data population of the municipality;
- Contained information list of every barangay needed by the agency; and
- Has a user-friendly interface and design.

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